

Deliverable 3.1

Basal Limestone Reef Design

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1 Introduction

The EU-co-funded LIFE NatuReef project aims to apply at a demonstration level the best practices available to restore native oyster and sabellariid reefs in a rare, non-urbanized, coastal stretch of the northern Adriatic coast: the Bevano river mouth (Ravenna municipality, Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy), which is a SAC and SPA under the EU Natura 2000 (IT4070009). For the first time in the Mediterranean Sea, the project has a dual aim: to restore these habitats and their biodiversity, and to provide a nature-based solution for protecting the coast from erosion, which is particularly intense here. In the region, native oysters in shallow waters have been almost disappeared for centuries, and sabellariid reefs are rare and fragmented, representing marginal habitats that have lost most of their ecosystem functions. Besides the well-known ecosystem goods and services, as well as the social and economic benefits they may provide, both species are able to create three-dimensional reefs that retain sediments and dissipate wave energy, counteracting coastal erosion. As living structures, they have the potential to grow and adapt and, to some extent, counteract some of the effects of climate change, such as sea level rise and increased storm and flooding event frequency and intensity, thereby contributing to the resistance and resilience of the coastal marine ecosystem.

To achieve these multiple objectives, it was necessary to design a wide and intricate limestone substrate with iron cages appropriately sized and positioned according to the hydrodynamic, geomorphological, and sedimentary conditions, using numerical models based on precise surveys. The adults of *Ostrea edulis* used for restocking came from offshore natural banks. To repopulate *Sabellaria spinulosa*, aggregation nuclei originating from populations developing at the basis of nearby traditional breakwater reefs were transplanted. The effectiveness of the repopulation and the expected effects on the surrounding habitats and protected species are being monitored.

The primary aim of the project work package 3 “**Design and construction of the basal limestone reef**” is to provide for the design and construction of the basal limestone reef (BLR) over which the biogenic reefs will be implemented. The design of the BLR has been carried out by the municipality of RAVENNA, with the support of the Acqua Ingegneria, an engineering and design company with entirely public capital, and the UNIBO’s team of hydraulic engineers and geologists, who have both a long experience in the design of coastal defence structures and control of sedimentary regimes.

Before proceeding with the final design, in accordance with Italian law, the preliminary project was subjected to an **Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA, VIA in Italian)** by the Emilia-Romagna Region, as the competent body. The EIA process, chaired by the Emilia-Romagna Region and involving all the authorities and stakeholders, although it resulted in an extension of the project's timeframe, allowed for a co-design process that largely improved the initial proposal. With act 07/07/2025 - 1114 – DGR (Decree of the Emilia-Romagna Region), the

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procedure was successful. The entire EIA process (Reference Number PG.2024.0495328, Start Date 15/05/2024) is available for consultation on the following webpage:

<https://serviziambiente.regione.emilia-romagna.it/viavasweb/ricerca/dettaglio/6268>

After implementing the final requirements resulting from the EIA process, on August 26, 2025, with resolution no. 325 (Protocol no. 0183878/2025) of the of the municipal council, the Municipality of Ravenna adopted the **executive project** entitled “Works aimed at the restoration and conservation of marine and coastal habitats through the creation of an oyster and oaks reef at the mouth of the Bevano stream (LIFE NatuReef) - CUP C68H24000140001”.

The whole executive project includes 33 pdf documents (Fig. 1, see also Table 1), wrote in Italian, which are provided as separated attachments available at the project open access repository

<https://10.5281/zenodo.15121005>.

Fig. 1. Typical cover page of the executive project documents.

Below is provided an executive summary of the BLR executive project.

2 Executive summary: Basal Limestone Reef design overview

The executive design of the BLR was chosen based on a whole Environmental Impact Assessment process, which included an exhaustive study of the environmental conditions, ecological, geological and oceanographic processes, enforced regulations, and the possible impacts of different design alternatives, both during and after construction.

The chosen design alternative provides a flexible and modular solution, with a mattress structure, filled with 100/200 mm limestone stones (Fig. 2), of modular dimensions 5.00 x 2.00 x 0.30 m placed on multiple levels (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4). The dimensional characteristics favour a dissipation effect of the wave energy over a longer and less elevated path with respect to the seabed and a location that fits into the context of the pre-existing defence works in the area. The solution was designed to define the best conformation for all the sedimentological, hydraulic and hydrodynamic implications that could be generated, and at the same time create an ideal substrate for the settlement of native oysters and sabellaria worms.

Fig. 2. Sharp-edged limestone material (broken) size 100/200 mm.

Fig. 3. Non-homogeneous checkerboard modules (the pink modules have an elevation of 0.30 m while the grey ones have an elevation of 0.60 cm).

Fig. 4. Rendering of the final deployment layout.

Based on the bathymetric survey conducted on March 14, 2024, and previous surveys, as well as hydraulic and sedimentological modelling, the eroding coastal area immediately south of the existing defence structures was identified as the appropriate location for the BLR (Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7).

Fig. 5. Project location (Projection UTM33 WGS84).

Fig. 6. Project plan on DTM, surveyed March 14, 2024 (Projection UTM33 WGS84).

The structure will cover a total area of 100.00 x 48.00 m (4800 m²). The non-homogeneous but non-random arrangement of the modular elements will allow for the maximum possible surface area, while also avoiding the formation of undesirable currents during storm surges inside and on the structure.

The average erosion rate estimated in the central area of the study site is -2.3 ± 1.0 m/year, decreasing to negligible values in the southernmost segments. In the positioning area of the project reef, the average erosion rate was -1.5 ± 1.1 m/year from 1998 to 2019.

Numerical modelling of the wave propagation on the reef and the hydrodynamic induced were used to support the design (e.g., Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Wave height is reduced in the area behind the reef.

The reasons that defined the positioning of the work can be summarized:

- The need for the subsequent settlement of native oysters to colonise the structure was fundamental for the choice of submergence, as the oysters, for their survival, should never be emerged, therefore considering a low tide even greater than - 50 cm and a colonial development of oysters of 20/30 cm in height, it was deemed appropriate to maintain an additional water level of 40/50 cm (therefore 1.40 m in total) in order to guarantee a minimum level of water coverage even during storm surges.
- The positioning at a depth greater than -2.00 m, with development towards the sea side, is due to the type of maritime vehicles that can be used on site, which in any case rarely have a draft lower than approximately 2.00/2.20 m, therefore at full load, in order to operate safely and with a working window, they must adapt their operations to the tidal phases, starting with the rising phase, thus being able to

take advantage of the coincidence of the unloading of the vehicle and therefore a lower draft of the same.

- The structure will be constructed by installing mats measuring 5.00 x 2.00 x 0.30 m each, made of wire mesh, placed side by side. Before installation, the mats will be filled and packaged with sharp-edged limestone material measuring 100/200 mm, creating an appropriate void ratio to create an environment suitable for both housing and growing the oysters and sabellaria.
- The technical characteristics of the wire mesh guarantee a lifespan of at least 10 years, to allow for complete colonization by oysters, as well as for dynamic stability in the face of wave motion and currents.
- The location is also suitable for the possibility of access via the beach for potential visitors (divers, freedivers and snorkelers).

The design has some technical features that make this infrastructure unique from a hydrodynamic perspective in the panorama of other previous and already existing coastal defence structures:

- The intervention is carried out from a depth of approximately 2.00 m, and consequently much closer to the shoreline.
- The submergence varies between 1.20 m and 2.40 m in the most offshore area. In these results, the transmission coefficient is defined as the ratio of the wave height behind and in front of the work, but it should be considered that the distance is much greater and therefore over this distance, the waves are also modified by shoaling.
- The transmission coefficient (K_t) values obtained are in the order of 0.38 and 0.41 for the conditions examined and decreases by approximately 10% when comparing the simulation without reef to those with reef.
- The total volume eroded in simulation without reef is more than double that of the case with reef.
- An intense current due to breaking is observed on the infrastructure, and a reduction in front, for which a reduction in transport is expected.

Attachments

Table 1. Documents Included in the executive project.

N.	Title (Italian)	Title (English)
1	EL PE Elenco elaborati	EL PE List of Documents
2	RG PE Relazione generale	RG PE General Report
3	RT PE Relazione tecnica	RT PE Technical Report
4	RSO PE Relazione di sostenibilità dell'opera	RSO PE Sustainability Report
5	DFOT PE Documentazione fotografica	DFOT PE Photographic Documentation
6	PDM PE Piano di occupazione aree P.D.M.	PDM PE Area Occupation Plan (PDM)
7	PMO PE Piano di Manutenzione dell'opera	PMO PE Maintenance Plan (PMO)
8	PMG PE Piano Preliminare di Monitoraggio Geotecnico e Strutturale	PMG PE Preliminary Geotechnical and Structural Monitoring Plan
9	PMA PE Piano Preliminare di Monitoraggio Ambientale	PMA PE Preliminary Environmental Monitoring Plan (PMA)
10	SIA PE Studio di Impatto Ambientale	SIA PE Environmental Impact Assessment (SIA)
11	All. 1 SIA PE S.N.T. - Sintesi non Tecnica	Annex 1 PE SNT - Non-Technical Summary
12	All. 2 SIA PE Studio di Incidenza Ambientale	Annex 2 PE Environmental Impact Assessment
13	SC PE Schema di Contratto	SC PE Draft Contract (SC)
14	CSA_I PE Capitolato Speciale d'Appalto - Parte I Amministrativa	CSA_I PE Special Tender Specifications - Administrative Part I
15	CSA_II PE Capitolato Speciale d'Appalto - Parte II Tecnica	CSA_II PE Special Tender Specifications - Technical Part II
16	CAM PE Relazione sui Criteri Ambientali Minimi CAM	CAM PE Report on Minimum Environmental Criteria (CAM)
17	DNSH PE Relazione sul rispetto dei principio del D.N.S.H.	DNSH PE Report on Compliance with the DNSH Principles (DNSH)
18	AP PE Analisi Prezzi	AP PE Price Analysis
19	EP PE Elenco Prezzi	EP PE Price List
20	QIM PE Quadro Incidenza Manodopera	QIM PE Labor Incidence Table
21	CME PE Computo Metrico Estimativo	CME PE Cost Estimate
22	QTE PE Quadro Tecnico Economico	QTE PE Technical-Economic Table
23	CRP PE Cronoprogramma	CRP PE Time Schedule
24	T_1001 PE Inquadramento territoriale generale	T_1001 PE General Territorial Overview
25	T_1002 PE Inquadramento territoriale - Corografia	T_1002 PE Territorial Overview - Chorography
26	T_1003 PE Planimetria con indicazione punti di scatto	T_1003 PE Plan with Trigger Points
27	T_1004 PE Stato di fatto - rilievo topografico	T_1004 PE Current Status - Topographic Survey
28	T_1005 PE Progetto - Planimetria e sezioni	T_1005 PE Project - Plan and Sections
29	T_1006 PE Progetto - Disegno di dettaglio dei singoli elementi	T_1006 PE Project - Detailed Drawing of Individual Elements
30	T_1007 PE Progetto - dettaglio di schema di posa dei singoli elementi	T_1007 PE Project - Detailed Installation Diagram of Individual Elements
31	PSC PE Piano di Sicurezza e Coordinamento PSC	PSC PE Safety and Coordination Plan
32	T_1008 PE Layout di cantiere	T_1008 PE Construction Site Layout
33	MGA PE Manuale di gestione ambientale del cantiere	MGA PE Construction Site Environmental Management Manual

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